

Dancing with strangers? Initial trust and the formation of initial ties between new ventures and corporate venture capitalists

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Variables Table

Type	Variable Name	Variable Description
Dependent	<i>Realized_{ij}</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if CVC investor i invested in venture j (i.e., formed a realized tie with venture j), 0 otherwise.
Independent	<i>Trust</i>	Variable computed as measure of country-of-origin stereotypical trust obtained from a survey conducted by Eurobarometer in 1996. Specifically, respondents were asked the following question: “I would like to ask you a question about how much trust you have in people from various countries. For each, please tell me whether you have a lot of trust, some trust, not very much trust, or no trust at all.” We recode the answers to the trust question from 1 (i.e., no trust at all) to 4 (i.e., a lot of trust), and then calculate the mean value of the responses for each pair of countries. <i>Trust</i> is the mean level of trust that citizens in the country where the ventures are located have in people from the country where the parent companies of the CVC investors are located.
	<i>IPP regime</i>	Dummy equal to 1 for ventures operating in industries with effective legal defenses provided by IPP laws, i.e., pharmaceuticals, biotechnology, biological products, chemical products, surgical instruments, and other medical equipment, 0 otherwise.

	<i>IVC centrality</i>	Variable computed as the maximum normalized eigenvector centrality of all participating IVC investors up to the focal round in each venture.
	<i>CVC centrality</i>	Variable computed as the maximum normalized eigenvector centrality of each CVC investor up to the focal round. This variable, each year, takes the same values across all dyads in which a given CVC investor is involved.
	<i>Direct social ties</i>	Dummy equal to 1 when the number of previous co-investments between a focal CVC investor <i>i</i> and the IVC investors to which a focal venture <i>j</i> is affiliated is higher than or equal to 1 (i.e., when the focal CVC investor has at least one direct social tie with one or more IVC investors backing the focal venture), and 0 otherwise.
	<i>Indirect social ties</i>	Dummy equal to 1 when a focal CVC investor <i>i</i> has no direct ties with the IVC investors backing the focal venture <i>j</i> , but there is a co-investment history (i.e., at least one common investment) between (at least one of) these IVC investors and (at least one of) other IVC investors that previously syndicated one or more VC investments with the focal CVC investor <i>i</i> , but did not invest in venture <i>j</i> .
Control	<i>Venture age</i>	Variable computed as the (natural logarithm of the) number of years since the founding of the venture and controls for venture maturity.
	<i>Citation weighted patent stock</i>	Variable computed as the sum of the annual successful (i.e., granted) patent applications for each venture <i>j</i> in the EPO, dated at the application year, where applications are weighted by its forward citations five years after filing, and discounted using a 15% knowledge-depreciation rate.
	<i>Distance</i>	Variable computed as the (natural logarithm of the) geographical distance in thousands of kilometers between the focal venture <i>j</i> and the headquarters of the CVC investor <i>i</i> 's parent company.
	<i>Industry overlap</i>	Variable equal to 1 if venture <i>j</i> and the parent company of CVC investor <i>i</i> operate in the same industry (3-digit NACE Rev), and 0 otherwise. If there are more industry codes for one venture or parent company of the focal CVC investor, we set Industry overlap to 1 if there is any match in the industry classification codes.
	<i>Interdependence</i>	Variable computed as the sum, in a three-year window before each focal tie (either realized or unrealized), of i) the ratio between the number of CVC investments in ventures in sector <i>j</i> by CVC investors whose parent companies are in sector <i>i</i> and the total number of CVC investments in ventures in sector <i>j</i> ; and ii) the ratio between the number of CVC investments in ventures in sector <i>j</i> by CVC investors whose parent companies are in sector <i>i</i> and the total number of CVC investments by CVC investors whose parent companies are in sector <i>i</i> .
	<i>Round</i>	Variable equal to the ordinal count of the current financing round and controls for the investment stage.

	<i>Prior CVC investors</i>	Dummy variable equal to 1 if the focal venture received a CVC investment in any prior round, and 0 otherwise.
	<i>CVC to IVC inflow</i>	Variable computed as the ratio of the annual number of CVC investments to the annual number of IVC investments in each country-year.
Control in robustness checks	<i>CVC size</i>	Variable computed as the (natural logarithm of the) ratio of the sales of the parent company of the focal CVC investor to the average sales of all firms in the industry (3-digit NACE Rev).
	<i>CVC subsidiary</i>	Dummy equal to 1 if the CVC program is a wholly owned subsidiary, 0 otherwise.
	<i>Investment manager-level trust</i>	Variable computed as the average level of stereotypical trust from the new venture j's country toward the home countries of all investment managers of a focal CVC investor i.
	<i>Round size</i>	Variable computed as the investment amount of a focal round.
	<i>Common native language</i>	Variable obtained from the study by Melitz and Toubal (2014).
	<i>Common spoken language</i>	Variable obtained from the study by Melitz and Toubal (2014).
	<i>Domestic</i>	Dummy variable equal to 1 if new venture j and CVC investor i' parent companies are in the same country, 0 otherwise.
	<i>Neighboring countries</i>	Dummy variable equal to 1 if new venture j and CVC investor i' parent companies are in neighboring countries, 0 otherwise.
	<i>Power distance index</i>	Variable obtained from the study by Hofstede (2010).
	<i>Individualism vs. collectivism</i>	Variable obtained from the study by Hofstede (2010).
	<i>Masculinity vs. femininity</i>	Variable obtained from the study by Hofstede (2010).
	<i>Uncertainty avoidance index</i>	Variable obtained from the study by Hofstede (2010).
	<i>Long-term orientation vs. short-term or.</i>	Variable obtained from the study by Hofstede (2010).
	<i>Indulgence versus restraint</i>	Variable obtained from the study by Hofstede (2010).
	<i>Civil vs. common law</i>	Variable obtained from the study by La Porta et al. (1998).
	<i>Rule of law</i>	Variable obtained from the study by La Porta et al. (1998).
	<i>Efficiency of judicial system</i>	Variable obtained from the study by La Porta et al. (1998).
	<i>Risk of contract repudiation</i>	Variable obtained from the study by La Porta et al. (1998).
	<i>Risk of expropriation</i>	Variable obtained from the study by La Porta et al. (1998).
<i>CVC trust</i>	Variable computed as the mean level of trust that citizens in the country where the parent of the focal CVC investor i is	

		located have in people from the country where the focal new venture j is located.
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